

Post-Harvest Manipulation of *Iris Rhizome*

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White dry rhizome (Photo by Luigi Favale)

Iris pallida Lam. rhizome is a profitable crop in Mediterranean areas producing around 3.5 Mg ha⁻¹. Together with the cultivation operations of planting, weeding and harvesting, the manual skill of the operations on the rhizomes represents a further limit to the ability of iridaceous crops to spread. In fact, in July of the third year, the harvest is generally carried out with a manual tool (two-pronged hoe called the "obediente") that opens the crucial phases of the preparation of the product for saling and the propagation of the vegetative material for the subsequent cultivation planting. The rhizomes are separated by the numerous vegetative shoots of the plant (agamic propagation) named "cuttings". These are placed in dry places for subsequent September planting. The rhizomes are coarsely cleaned of the earth, deprived of the roots and soaked in water for a finer cleaning. At this point, traditionally, the process leads to the preparation of black or white rhizomes. The black rhizome is not peeled but sliced and left to dry. The white rhizome, on the other hand, is hulled and then sliced for drying. The two different preparations are linked to different end-product industry demand. On the one hand, the perfume industry that requires black for the production of iris butter; on the other, the distilleries that flavour liqueurs with white powder. Whatever the destination, the rhizome dehydrated and aged for few months is a raw material that requires a lot of labour but, if of excellent quality, it fetches extremely attractive prices on the market. Thus, the *Iris pallida* species appears as an adequate crop to be cultivated in orchards agroforestry farms.

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